

TECTONIC SETTING AND ISOTOPIC SOURCES (Sm-Nd) OF EDIACARAN BLACK SERIES IN THE SW OF IBERIAN MASSIF (OBEJO-VALSEQUILLO DOMAIN)

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In the SW of the Iberian Massif, the Obejo-Valsequillo Domain is part of an allochthonous upper terrane located above ophiolites thrust in turn above a basal terrane containing high-P units. These terranes define an orogenic pile generated during the main stages of the Variscan deformation, the tectonic event that formed the large orogen associated to the final assembly of Pangea. Both the basal and the upper terranes are considered of peri-Gondwanan origin, but the tectonic setting and isotopic sources of part of the sedimentary series included in these terranes are in some cases poorly constrained. This is specially the case of the sedimentary series of the upper terrane, where very scarce information about the major and trace element composition and the Sm-Nd isotope sources exists. However, several papers discussed recently the location of this terrane along the Gondwanan margin according to U-Pb geochronology and Hf composition of detrital zircons. Locations in the proximity of the Sahara Craton and West African Craton have been considered.

The stratigraphic record of the upper terrane in SW Iberia is characterized by the presence of a thick sedimentary series ranging in age between Ediacaran and Carboniferous times. Located below of well dated Early Cambrian deposits, the lowest and oldest unconformable part of this series contains a dark section defined as the Black Series, with dark shales and greywackes, black quartzites and intercalations of black cherts and basalts. It appears variably deformed and metamorphosed but well preserved levels exist where the record of primary sedimentary features can still be recognized. The Black Series appears frequently intruded by medium to small sized granitic bodies and other minor mafic-intermediate igneous massifs with Ediacaran and Early Cambrian ages. They suggest deposition in an active setting probably related to the activity of a peri-Gondwanan magmatic arc. However this setting and the associated isotopic sources should be confirmed for the Black Series using geochemical data obtained for specific compositions. This contribution presents new major and trace geochemical data and Sm-Nd isotopic compositions for 16 metagreywackes from the Black Series of the Obejo-Valsequillo Domain. These samples were collected in the three localities where the presence of this Ediacaran series is known (Valsequillo, Palomas and Villar del Rey), and they provide significant information for a better understanding of the origin of the SW Iberia Black Series.

Keywords: Ediacaran Black Series, Isotopic geochemistry (Sm-Nd), SW Iberian Massif.